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BUILDINGS OF THE CENTER FOR PUBLIC SERVICES, BUILT IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE CHINESE CITY OF KUN'SHAN)

A.O.Khasanov¹

¹Doctor of Philosophy in Architecture, Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction, Izzat Bekturdiyev M.²

² teacher, Urganch State University,

Abstract: This article analyzes the typology, layout, advantages, and disadvantages of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" building in Kushan city, Jiangsu Province, Republic of China.

Keywords: Building architecture, interior, floor plan, design, project construction, problems, advantages, building codes, master plan planning solutions.

Government" in Kunshan, Jiangsu Province, Republic of China The Public Services Center, known as the "Affairs Service Centre," mainly consists of four towers and a podium with a total area of 102,000 square meters. It includes more than 20 municipal offices. These include social security, tax, state security, border access, state resource exchange, investment and development, market access, general management, and other services. The first figure shows the general view.

Figure 1. Building of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" in the city of Kunshan.

The project began in 2009 and continued for two years. Song Yi, Chief Architect Construction of the project was started by

Shanghai Domaim Think Design in 2011 and commissioned in 2019.

Figure 2. Plan of the 1st floor of the "Government Affairs Service Center" building in the city of Kun'shan

The first floor of the building is designed in modern style, and the main entrance consists of three parts. The first entrance is located in the eastern part of the building, the second entrance is located in the north of the building, and the third entrance is in the southwest of the building. After the entrance, there is a covered vestibule at a height of several floors (2). Following it are elevators for ascending to the floors (3). Next to it is the second hall (4). A kitchen is located in the southern part of the building, and a restaurant is located next to it (5-6). In the northeastern

part of the building, a descent into the basement designed for parking cars is designed (7). After the entrance from the east, there is a public hall (8). After this hall, on the right side, there is a special room that ensures

the safety of those working in this building and visitors (9). To the south of the building, a separate exit is designed for cars to exit the basement (10).

Figure 3. Plan of the basement of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" building in the city of Kun'shan

In one-third of the building's basement plan, parking space is allocated for cars (1). Following it are elevators for ascending to the floors (2). Training hall (3). In the western part of the building is a scenic waiting area and a gallery (4-5). Several special halls are located in the basement part of the building (6). There is also a reception room on the basement floor (7). The cofeshop and kitchen for customers are also located on the basement floor (8-9). In several places, a room is also allocated for discussions (10).

Figure 4. Interior of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" building in the city of Kun'shan

Figure 5. Interior of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" building in the city of Kun'shan

As for the interior of the building, the interior environment of the room shown in Figures 4-5 above is mainly used in bright colors and natural lighting. The project

consists of a multitude of public services, with an inevitable emphasis on "sunlight" and "openness." The perimeter of the atrium, as a result of the addition of fences from the level of the foundation to the second floor, shaded the sun, lightened the adjacent building to the west, and directed the lines of view to the pool with bamboo and lotus to the east. This courtyard is designed to recreate the scenery depicted in the ancient book Yushan Yajida in Kunsha in an installed frame. At the same

time, the grilles made it easier to adapt to the darkness due to the contrast of light when exiting the basement. The lattice shape locally symbolizes eastern tranquility and order.

Green plane trees, corresponding to the aesthetics of the eastern courtyard, were planted in the waiting area, and thanks to sunlight and landscaping, the difference between the interior and exterior of the building was eliminated.

China – Kunshan “Government Affairs Service Centre”

Table of Advantages and Disadvantages

Indicators	Advantages	Disadvantages
Architecture and Composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Matches to correct answer, transparent, clear spatial logical organization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large scale (102,000 m²) construction leads to high operating costs, complex planning
Functional Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services on the ground floor, auxiliary departments on upper floors; clear flow separation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wide placement of functions may result in excessive walking distances in some cases
Urban Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well-connected to transport, integrated with public spaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large scale may reduce visual harmony with the surrounding environment
Service and Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More than 20 institutions gathered in one place, “one-stop-shop” approach fully operational 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High visitor flow during peak times leads to queues
Engineering Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modern technologies, energy-efficient systems applied 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial investment and maintenance costs are high
Navigation and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Central atrium, visual guidance, security systems effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large scale complicates orientation for new users

Conclusion

Typological analysis of the experience of public service centers built in foreign countries, in particular in the People's Republic of China, shows that buildings of this type represent a new architectural model of modern public administration and communication with the public. The analysis conducted using the example of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" in the city of Kun'shan confirms that centralization, functional flexibility, and technological integration are the main typological features in the formation of public service centers.

This building is typologically characterized as a large-scale, multifunctional, and vertically developed

administrative complex. In it, the main planning factor is the service system based on the "single window" principle, which serves to accelerate the service process and simplify interdepartmental communication. The clear separation of functional zones by layers, spatial connections through the central atrium, and user flow management solutions reflect the modern typological approach characteristic of public service centers.

Also, the experience of Kunshan shows that foreign public service centers are not limited to administrative functions, but are also being formed as a public space. The presence of open lobbies, waiting rooms, dining areas, galleries, and green spaces makes the building an active element of urban life. This situation shows that public service

buildings are moving away from the traditional closed and formal character and are transitioning to user-oriented architecture.

One of the important aspects identified during the typological analysis is the problems associated with the large size and centralized structure of the building. Large scale leads to increased operating costs, longer user routes, and, in some cases, more complex orientation. This indicates the need to develop flexible typological solutions when designing public service centers, taking into account the scale of the territory, the population, and the volume of services.

In conclusion, the building of the "Government Affairs Service Centre" in the city of Kun'shan can be assessed as a modern, stable, and integrated typological model for the formation of public service centers in foreign countries. This experience has important scientific and practical significance in improving the architectural and typological solutions of public service center buildings in the conditions of Uzbekistan, in particular, in centralizing services, increasing user convenience, strengthening its role as a public space, and introducing the principles of energy efficiency.

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